

Synthesis, structure, reactivity and electrochemical studies of oxovanadium(IV) chelates with some carboxamide derivatives

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Abstract : Oxovanadium(IV) chelates of (2Z)-4-(2-acetylhydrazino)-4-oxobut-2-enoic acid (AOBEH), 4-(2-acetylhydrazino)-4-oxobutanoic acid (AOBAH), 2-[(2-acetylhydrazino)carbonyl]benzoic acid (AHCBH), (2Z)-4-[(2-cyanophenyl)amino]-4-oxobut-2-enoic acid (COBEH), 4-[(2-cyanophenyl)amino]-4-oxobutanoic acid (COBAH), 2-[(2-cyanophenyl)amino]carbonyl]benzoic acid (CACBH), (2Z)-4-(1H-benzimidazol-2-ylamino)-4-oxobut-2-enoic acid (BOBEH), 4-(1H-benzimidazol-2-ylamino)-4-oxobutanoic acid (BOBAH) and 2-[(1H-benzimidazol-2-ylamino)carbonyl]benzoic acid (BYCBH) have been prepared and characterized by elemental analysis, magnetic moments, IR, electronic, NMR, ESR spectra and thermal studies. The magnetic moments and electronic spectral studies suggest square pyramid geometry to all the oxovanadium(IV) complexes and distorted octahedral geometry to the vanadium(IV) complexes with O_4 and Cl_2O_4 as donor sets from the ligands. The electrochemical studies by cyclic voltammograms produced irreversible single oxidation peak for V^{IV} - V^V vs SCE ranging from 0.43-0.64 V rationalized by the basicity of ligands.

Keywords : Oxovanadium(IV), carboxamide, electrochemical studies.

The recent interest in the coordination chemistry of the oxovanadium(IV) complexes with O, O; O, N and N, N donor ligands is due to its growing applications in catalysis^{1,2} and therapeutics³. Vanadium in traces has multiple biological roles⁴, therapeutic value in small doses and toxic in excess. Vanadium containing compounds have this utility as insulin mimetic^{5,6} and antiameobic agent⁷. It is also representative of a new class of non-platinum metal antitumor agents⁸. V^V - V^{IV} / V^{IV} - V^{III} redox systems are very significant from reactivity point of view. A comprehensive report on biochemical redox profile of vanadium has appeared recently⁹. Distortion in geometry of oxovanadium(IV) complexes from trigonal bipyramidal, square pyramidal to octahedral is also a subject of interest for structural studies^{10,11}. The chemistry of oxovanadium(IV) has received considerable attention¹² as the VO^{2+} can form VOL_4 , VOL_5 and VOL_6 type of complexes¹³. We have undertaken the systematic studies of transition metal complexes with biologically active amide group ligands derived from corresponding anhydrides and various substituted amines. In continuation of our work¹⁴⁻¹⁸, the present investigation describes the synthesis, characterization and electrochemical studies of some oxovanadium(IV) and vanadium(IV) complexes with

carboxamide ligands listed below : (i) (2Z)-4-(2-acetylhydrazino)-4-oxobut-2-enoic acid (AOBEH), (ii) 4-(2-acetylhydrazino)-4-oxobutanoic acid (AOBAH), (iii) 2-[(2-acetylhydrazino)carbonyl]benzoic acid (AHCBH), (iv) (2Z)-4-[(2-cyanophenyl)amino]-4-oxobut-2-enoic acid (COBEH), (v) 4-[(2-cyanophenyl)amino]-4-oxobutanoic acid (COBAH), (vi) 2-[(2-cyanophenyl)amino]carbonyl]benzoic acid (CACBH), (vii) (2Z)-4-(1H-benzimidazol-2-ylamino)-4-oxobut-2-enoic acid (BOBEH), (viii) 4-(1H-benzimidazol-2-ylamino)-4-oxobutanoic acid (BOBAH) and (ix) 2-[(1H-benzimidazol-2-ylamino)carbonyl]benzoic acid (BYCBH).

Results and discussion

All the complexes of oxovanadium(IV) and vanadium(IV) are crystalline non-hygroscopic and stable at room temperature. The colour of the complexes varied from light green to light blue or snuff. The complexes were freely soluble in DMF and DMSO but insoluble in common organic solvents. The analytical data for metal, carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen of complexes are presented in Table 1. The theoretical values of the elements in the complexes are calculated on the assumption that the metal combines with the ligand in 1 : 2 ratio. The

- R = CH₃CONH- for (AOBEH)
 R = *o*-C₆H₅CN for (COBEH)
 R = 1*H*-Benzimidazol-2-yl amino for (BOBEH)

- R = CH₃CONH- for (AOBAH)
 R = *o*-C₆H₅CN for (COBAH)
 R = 1*H*-Benzimidazol-2-yl amino for (BOBAH)

- R = CH₃CONH- for (AHCBH)
 R = *o*-C₆H₅CN for (CACBH)
 R = 1*H*-Benzimidazol-2-yl amino for (BYCBH)

complexes of AOBEB, AOBAB and COBAB are further associated with water molecules. It is clear from the experimental values that they are in good agreement with the calculated ones. The molar conductance values of the complexes in DMSO at 10⁻³ M concentration are recorded in the range of 8.0–15.0 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ suggesting that they are non-electrolytes¹⁹. The reactions of the vanadyl complexes, **1a-3a** with SOCl₂ resulted in new products that showed no characteristic absorption of ν(V=O) at 900–960 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectra. The solution of complexes was made in methanol to check the reactivity and substitutional behavior against amine, chloro, aqua, thiocyanato and hydroxy ligands. Reaction was monitored by observing the change in the color or precipitation.

Reaction with dil. NH₃(aq) : Oxovanadium complexes

of AHCBH, CACBH and BYCBH do not react with dil. aqueous ammonia on keeping for 1 h, at 25 °C but the complexes of rest of the ligands react slowly. All the three complexes react poorly even on heating up to 50 °C.

Reaction with dil. HCl : The VO-BOBE, BOBA and BYCB do not react with dil. HCl even on remaining for 1 h or heating up to 50 °C. The complexes of AOBEB, AOBAB and AHCBH react very slowly when compared to the complexes of COBEH, COBAH and CACBH and the reactivity of these six complexes increases slowly with increase in temperature up to 50 °C.

Reaction with H₂O : None of the oxovanadium complexes were found to react with water even on keeping for 1 h heating up to 40 °C. The complexes of AOBEB, COBEH and BOBEH react very slowly at a temperature above 40 °C.

The TGA and DTA were recorded for all the oxovanadium(IV) complexes and the decomposition temperature of the complexes determined in this laboratory are reported in Table 1. These values are close to those observed in the thermograms (Fig. 1). The absence of endothermic peaks in DSC without mass loss in TGA indicates that the complexes do not have characteristic melting points but decompose. It can be seen that the complexes of AOBEB, AOBAB and COBAH undergo decomposition in two stages. Initial weight loss in the temperature range of 70–120 °C with endothermic peak in DTA corresponds to lattice water. These complexes show another weight loss at 250–500 °C with exothermic peak in DTA corresponding to loss of organic moiety. The ultimate pyrolysis product (600 °C) in oxygenated atmosphere for all the cases is vanadium pentoxide. This fact is confirmed by their DTA curves which do not show an endothermic peak at a temperature above 600 °C. The initial decomposition temperatures of the complexes vary within a narrow range and based on the values observed, the stability order of the complexes is in the order : AOBEB < AOBAB < AHCBH < COBEH < COBAH < CACBH < BOBEH < BOBAH < BYCBH. This may be due to the steric factors such as bulkiness of the groups attached to the ligating groups²⁰.

Room temperature magnetic moments of oxovanadium(IV) and vanadium(IV) complexes lie in the range of 1.66–1.83 B.M. These values suited for monomeric complexes with one unpaired electron. The oxovanadium complexes of COBEH, BOBEH and BYCBH exhibit μ_{eff} values (1.66–1.69 B.M.) which are slightly less than the spin only value (1.73 B.M.) and this may be attributed to the completely quenched orbital contribution²¹.

Table 1. Physical, analytical and electrochemical data of VO^{IV} and V^{IV} complexes

Sl no.	Complex/ Colour	Initial decomp. temp. (°C)	Found (Calcd.)%				μ_{eff} (B.M.)	E_{pa} (V)
			C	H	N	M		
1.	[VO(COBE) ₂] Green	285	53.69 (53.52)	2.83 (2.79)	11.30 (11.00)	12.86 (12.96)	1.69	0.61
2.	[VO(COBA) ₂].H ₂ O Bluish green	295	51.26 (51.40)	3.10 (3.04)	10.87 (10.80)	9.90 (10.05)	1.76	0.52
3.	[VO(CACB) ₂] Snuff	305	60.30 (60.20)	3.01 (3.06)	9.38 (9.41)	8.54 (8.41)	1.76	0.64
4.	[VO(AOBE) ₂].2H ₂ O Snuff	250	32.35 (32.50)	4.14 (4.18)	12.58 (12.50)	11.96 (11.85)	1.83	0.35
5.	[VO(AOBA) ₂].2H ₂ O Green	268	33.41 (33.46)	4.64 (4.32)	12.99 (13.06)	11.83 (11.80)	1.76	0.23
6.	[VO(AHCB) ₂] Light blue	285	53.69 (53.52)	2.83 (2.79)	11.30 (11.00)	12.86 (12.96)	1.69	0.61
7.	[VO(BOBE) ₂] Pale green	308	50.09 (50.05)	3.03 (3.00)	15.93 (16.00)	9.67 (9.71)	1.68	0.53
8.	[VO(BOBA) ₂] Bluish green	315	49.60 (49.81)	3.76 (3.71)	15.81 (15.86)	9.60 (9.51)	1.73	0.48
9.	[VO(BYCB) ₂] Green	320	57.40 (57.51)	3.18 (3.14)	13.39 (13.42)	8.13 (8.16)	1.69	0.58
1a	[V(COBE) ₂ Cl ₂] Yellowish green	290	47.72 (47.85)	3.09 (3.00)	10.14 (10.02)	9.23 (9.33)	1.65	0.60
2a	[V(COBA) ₂ Cl ₂] Brown	300	47.70 (47.84)	3.20 (3.23)	10.10 (10.07)	9.20 (9.17)	1.67	0.59
3a	[V(CACB) ₂ Cl ₂] Brown	315	54.80 (54.87)	3.25 (3.35)	8.60 (8.53)	7.80 (7.77)	1.70	0.61

Fig. 1. (a) TGA and (b) DSC curves of [VO(COBA)₂].H₂O.

A useful comparison of the spectra of the ligands and the complexes resulted following information regarding

coordination through various groups. The IR spectra of the ligands exhibit bands at $1700 \pm 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1300 \pm 30 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{OH})$ stretching frequencies. These bands are replaced by bands at $1550 \pm 15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1380 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{COO}^-)$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO}^-)$ (in all the complexes) suggesting deprotonation and coordination of the carboxyl group. This is supported by the disappearance of the signal corresponding to carboxyl proton of ligands in the respective complexes in their ¹H NMR spectra. The band (in the ligand spectra) due to amide $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ around 1650 cm^{-1} shifted to lower frequency by $30\text{--}50 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all the complexes while band due to amide $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$ shifted to higher frequency indicating the involvement of carbonyl oxygen of the amide group in coordination. A characteristic non-ligand sharp band at $900\text{--}960 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes is assigned to $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$. Some new bands of weaker intensity in the region of $400\text{--}600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the oxovanadium complexes give inferences about V-O and V-N bonding.

The IR spectra of vanadium(IV) complexes (**1a-3a**) obtained by the reaction of oxovanadium(IV) complexes with SOCl_2 , showed absorptions characteristic of the ligand and the complex. The conspicuous observation is the absence of the strong absorption around 900 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ vibrations. The far IR spectra of the three complexes show characteristic absorption of $\nu(\text{V}-\text{O})$ around 380 cm^{-1} . The new band in the region of $250\text{--}300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the vanadium(IV) complexes inferences about V-Cl bonds in these complexes.

The electronic spectra of oxovanadium(IV) complexes exhibit bands in the regions : $13800\text{--}14290$, $16800\text{--}20000$ and $23160\text{--}24000\text{ cm}^{-1}$; the transitions have been assigned to be due to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$, respectively. But all the three vanadium(IV) complexes reported now, exhibit only one absorption band between 11350 and 12820 cm^{-1} . The difference in the spectra of these oxovanadium(IV) and vanadium(IV) complexes reported in the present paper may be ascribed to square pyramidal and distorted octahedral geometry of the complexes (Structure 1).

The ESR spectra of oxovanadium(IV) (d^1) complexes are well resolved (Fig. 2) at liquid nitrogen temperature when compared to that at room temperature in exhibiting all the eight hyperfine lines. The calculated values^{22,23} of g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} , g_{av} , A_0 , A_{\parallel} , A_{\perp} , K , α^2 and β^2 are given in Table 2. The $g_{av} = 1/3 (2g_{\perp} + g_{\parallel})$. The values are typical of the spectra displayed by square pyramid oxovanadium(IV) complexes with the impaired electron in an orbital of d_{xy} character. In the square pyramid complexes with C_4 symmetry, the $\text{V}=\text{O}$ bond is along z and other four donor atoms (O_4) are along x and y axes. The variation in Fermi contact term, K , is in the range 0.8 to 0.9 and the plot of K vs $1/\Delta E_1$ (ΔE_1 is taken from the electronic spectra) gave a straight line. This indicates that as the in-plane ligand field increases, as measured by ΔE_1 , the $4s$ bonding contribution to the isotropic contact term decreases²⁴. The values indicate that K is directly proportional to A_0 . The g_{\perp} term does not vary to a great extent from complex to complex. This quantity is related mostly to the axial $\text{V}=\text{O}$ interaction and is not directly related to the in-plane ligands. The g_0 value in all complexes is in good agreement with the reported values^{25,26} which suggests that the unpaired electron is present in the d_{xy} orbital. This observation supports the geometry made on the basis of electronic spectra²⁷. The calculated in-plane π -bonding coefficient value (β^2) does not deviate much from unity for all the complexes, the β^2 value remains constant and spans the region from 0.93 to 1.00 . Essentially

the delocalization of electron into the ligand can be gauged from the in-plane σ -bonding coefficient (α^2) values. This follows the σ -donor strength of the ligand and it usually decreases as the covalent bonding increases. The molecular orbital coefficients also show that the metal ion has some covalent character in the ligand environment.

Electrochemistry :

The electrochemical properties of all the oxovanadium(IV) complexes were examined by cyclic voltammetry in DMF solution at a Pt working electrode and they exhibit a well defined irreversible oxidation peak due to $\text{V}^{\text{IV}}\text{--V}^{\text{V}}$ process. The oxovanadium(V) complexes so formed are unstable. The anodic peak potentials, E_{pa} are listed in Table 1. The E_{pa} values span in the range $0.23\text{--}0.64\text{ V}$ vs SCE. From the basicity point of view of the donor atoms of the ligands, it is expected that the electron density on the vanadium centre will be in the order : $\text{AOBAH} < \text{AOBEH} < \text{AHCBH} < \text{BOBAH} < \text{COBAH} < \text{BOBEH} < \text{BYCBH} < \text{COBEH} < \text{CACBH}$, and in fact, the E_{pa} values observed experimentally in the reverse order. So, from the comparison of E_{pa} values, it is evident that this value gradually decreases with the increase in basicity of the donor atom of amide oxygen (the others remaining invariant) and hence, the more basic atoms have tendency to stabilize VO^{3+} motif preferably than VO^{2+} motif and vice-versa. Two other distinct reduction peaks were also observed for all the maleic amide derivatives at high negative potentials, near -1.10 and -1.60 V due to electron transfer at the olefinic group (eq. (1) and (2)).

Fig. 2. (a) ESR spectrum of $[\text{VO}(\text{COBE})_2]$ at room temperature, (b) ESR spectrum of $[\text{VO}(\text{COBE})_2]$ at LNT.

Table 2. ESR parameters, isotropic contact term and molecular orbital coefficients of VO^{IV} and V^{IV} complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	g_0	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	A_0	A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}	K	α^2	β^2
1.	$[\text{VO}(\text{COBE})_2]$	1.97	1.95	1.98	116	196	76	0.81	0.65	0.98
2.	$[\text{VO}(\text{COBA})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	2.00	1.95	2.04	122	169	99	0.89	0.63	0.94
3.	$[\text{CO}(\text{CACB})_2]$	2.00	1.96	2.03	118	166	94	0.83	0.56	0.94
4.	$[\text{VO}(\text{AOBE})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	1.96	1.94	1.97	119	197	80	0.83	0.68	0.98
5.	$[\text{VO}(\text{AOBA})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	2.02	1.95	2.06	120	162	99	0.86	0.66	0.95
6.	$[\text{VO}(\text{AHCB})_2]$	2.00	1.96	2.02	115	145	100	0.80	0.57	0.96
7.	$[\text{VO}(\text{BOBE})_2]$	1.98	1.96	1.99	118	196	78	0.83	0.55	0.93
8.	$[\text{VO}(\text{BOBA})_2]$	1.99	1.95	2.01	119	195	81	0.83	0.64	0.97
9.	$[\text{VO}(\text{BYCB})_2]$	1.99	1.94	2.02	11	191	80	0.82	0.72	0.96
1a	$[\text{V}(\text{COBE})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	2.04	1.95	2.09	100	130	85	-	0.69	0.93

The reduced species do not appear to be stable enough to show the reversibility. From the absence of any electrochemical response for the succinamide and phthalicamide derivatives studied in this range confirms the reduction of olefinic group of maleicamide derivative.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in the study were of A.R. grade. The ligands used in complexation were prepared by reported methods. The solvents diethyl ether and methanol

were distilled by standard procedures before use. The nine ligands used in this work were prepared and

characterised by elemental analyses, IR, NMR and mass spectral data. The purity of the prepared compounds was checked by thin layer chromatography. Elemental analyses were performed at analytical and inorganic laboratory, Technical University of Berlin, Berlin, Germany. Conductivity measurements were made on Digisun digital conductivity meter DI-909. TG-DSC thermograms were recorded at IDL Chemicals, Hyderabad on Mettler-TA-2000C model. The IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets with a Perkin-Elmer-283 spectrophotometer in the range of 4000–200 cm^{-1} . Electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO using Shimadzu MPS-5000 spectrophotometer. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker WM 400 instrument at Technical University of Berlin, Berlin, Germany. ESR spectra were recorded on JEOL-JES-FE-3X spectrometer at University of Hyderabad, Hyderabad.

Synthesis of oxovanadium(IV) complexes :

Each of the ligand (5 mmol) was dissolved in 30 ml of methanol. The pH of the solution was adjusted to 6.0 by adding methanolic solution of NaOH. Metal salt ($\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (2.5 mmol) in methanol (25 mL) was added to the solution of the ligand with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 4–6 h at 70 °C. The micro crystals formed were suction filtered and washed several times with methanol followed by repeated washing with 1 : 1 diethyl ether, methanol mixture and dried in vacuo over anhydrous calcium chloride (yield 82–89%).

Preparation of vanadium(IV) complexes²⁸ :

Complex 1 (0.5 g) was suspended in 20 ml of dry benzene. 0.4 g of freshly distilled SOCl_2 was added with a syringe and stirred at 45 °C for about 2 h. The product (1a) was filtered and washed with dry benzene till it was free from traces of SOCl_2 in a quantitative yield. A similar procedure was applied to synthesize the complexes of 2a and 3a and isolated in good yields.

Conclusions :

The magnetic moments and electronic spectral studies suggest square pyramid geometry to all the oxovanadium(IV) complexes and distorted octahedral geometry to the vanadium(IV) complexes with O_4 and Cl_2O_4 as donor sets from the ligands. The irreversible single oxidation peak for $\text{V}^{\text{IV}}-\text{V}^{\text{V}}$ vs SCE ranging from 0.23–0.64 V obtained from the electrochemical studies by cyclic voltammograms is in consistence with the basicity of the ligands.

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